

HEREDITARY

HetERogeneous sEmantic Data integration for the guT-bRain interplaY

Deliverable 5.5

Querying Components

Version 1.10, 13.08.2025

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No GA 101137074. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

**Funded by
the European Union**

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

HetERogeneous sEMantic Data integration for the guT-bRain interplaY (HEREDITARY) develops novel approaches for analysis and exploration of multi-modal biomedical data. Multi-modality poses a challenge to data analysis, due to the divergent data types, scales, or levels of detail at which these may be given. Current approaches can represent multi-modal data in unified data structures, such as Knowledge Graphs (KGs), and tabular data. Due to the complex nature of the data, and also, expert-level interfaces like SQL and SPARQL to such data sets, users often have problems to effectively search, find, and discover insights in such data sets with ease.

In this HEREDITARY deliverable, we present novel approaches for effective user access to complex data, including retrieval, explanation, and comparison of data. Specifically, we leverage the potential of state of the art Large Language Models. We show how using natural language, users from novice to expert level, can express their information need in a natural language statement. The system applies these statements to create answers for the user, and can involve users in an information-seeking dialogue. Our approaches operate on KG data (e.g., as obtained from information extraction algorithms of large publication data), and on tabular data (e.g., structured complex patient information from clinical research). Preliminary evaluation shows the large potential of these approaches for retrieval and exploration in complex and multi-modal data. Building on this, in follow-up work we will refine, integrate and evaluate these querying components as part of requirement engineering, and scientific dissemination.

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

Deliverable ID	5.5
Deliverable Title	Querying Components
Work Package	WP 5
Lead Partner	TU Graz
Due Date	31.08.2025
Date of submission	13.08.2025
Deliverable Type	R – Report
Dissemination level	PU – Public

AUTHORS

Name	Organization
Tobias Schreck	TUGRAZ
Svetla Boytcheva	ONTO
Stefan Lengauer	TUGRAZ
Peter Waldert	TUGRAZ
Benedikt Kantz	TUGRAZ
Aleksis Datseris	ONTO
Tsvetelina Koleva	ONTO
Todor Primov	ONTO
Ivelina Nikolova-Koleva	ONTO
Juan Manuel Rodriguez (Internal reviewer)	AAU
Gianmaria Silvello (Contributor)	UNIPD

REVISION HISTORY

Version	Date	Author	Description
0.10	2025-02-28	Peter Waldert	Structure for deliverable
0.20	2025-07-18	All Authors	Complete draft including all components
0.30	2025-07-21	All Authors	Added summary and finalized for internal review
1.00	2025-08-01	All Authors	Revised and finalized with internal reviewer comments
1.10	2025-08-05	Gianmaria Silvello	Final check, layout fixes and minor changes

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Contents

1	Introduction	10
2	OnSET Query Editor	11
2.1	Introduction	11
2.2	Related Work	12
2.2.1	NLP Query Approaches	12
2.2.2	Visual Query Approaches	12
2.2.3	Graph Difference Views	13
2.3	Methodology	13
2.3.1	User Guidance	14
2.3.2	Graph Definition	15
2.3.3	Difference Graphs	15
2.3.4	Automatic Result Set Overview	16
2.3.5	Integration of a Natural Language Query System	16
2.3.6	User Interface	16
2.4	Implementation	16
2.5	Case study	18
2.6	Conclusion	19
2.7	Future Work	20
3	Graph Queries from Natural Language using Constrained Language Models & Evaluation	21
3.1	Introduction	21
3.2	Related Work	21
3.3	Methodology	22
3.3.1	Graph Extraction	23
3.3.2	Synthetic Evaluation Methodology	23
3.3.3	Constraining the LM	24
3.3.4	User Interface Integration	25
3.4	Results	25
3.5	Conclusion	27
3.6	Future Work	27
4	Talk to Your Graph: Natural Language Querying of Neuro Degenerative Diseases	28
4.1	Introduction	28
4.2	Related Work	28
4.3	Data	28
4.4	Methodology	30
4.4.1	Natural Language Querying	30
4.4.2	Implementation	31
4.5	Experiments and Results	35
4.6	Further work	35

5 Neurodegen-Vis: LLM-based, Privacy-Preserving Visual Exploration of High-Dimensional ALS, PD, MS Patient Data	39
5.1 Introduction	39
5.1.1 Dataset	40
5.1.2 Anonymisation using Differential Privacy	40
5.2 Related Work	41
5.3 Visualisation Approach & Methods	42
5.3.1 Natural Language Interface	42
5.4 Implementation	44
5.5 Use Case	44
5.6 Conclusion & Future Work	45
6 Summary and Further Development	45
References	46

List of Figures

1	Ontology and Sparse data Exploration Tool (OnSET) user flow. The user can select topics of interest and retrieve possible start links. These links are then expanded & constrained within an editor, which finally retrieves different instances of the searched graph.	13
2	User guidance within OnSET.	14
3	Query builder interface within OnSET.	17
4	Difference graph examples for the DBpedia ontology.	18
5	The Brainteaser Ontology (BTO) KG queried using the difference view to explore the relationship between different semantic attributes.	19
6	Prototype Graph extraction process from query.	22
7	Prototype graph extraction results over different query complexities and ontologies.	26
8	A data inventory organized as a map of data domains	29
9	BioGraphTalk KG	29
10	BioGraphTalk Class Relationship	30
11	BioGraphTalk Class Hierarchy	31
12	The High-Level Architecture of how GraphDBs NLQ works.	31
13	GraphDB Talk To Your Graph setup	32
14	TTYG Experiment 1 - What are protein protein interactions between ALS and Parkinson disease? - the answer summary in natural language	36
15	TTYG Experiment 1 - What are protein protein interactions between ALS and Parkinson disease? - the generated SPARQL query	37
16	TTYG Experiment 1 - What are protein protein interactions between ALS and Parkinson disease? - the generated SPARQL query run in GraphDB over BioGraphTalk	38
17	TTYG Experiment 1 - What are protein protein interactions between ALS and Parkinson disease? - visual exploration of the result in GraphDB over BioGraphTalk	38
18	Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis (ALS), Parkinson's Disease (PD), Multiple Sclerosis (MS) visualisation dashboard	39
19	The feature <i>language z-component</i> in the histogram view. Colour coded is the categorical feature z-diagnosis.	42

List of Tables

- 1 Comparison of query generation methods for Hermes 3B on DBpedia with one shot prompts. . . 26

Acronyms

- ALS** Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis. 7, 9
- BGP** Basic Graph Pattern. 9, 14, 15
- BRAINTEASER** Bringing Artificial Intelligence home for a better care of amyotrophic lateral sclerosis and multiple sclerosis. 9
- BTO** Braitteaser Ontology. 7, 9, 14, 18–20, 25, 26
- CEST-MRI** Chemical Exchange Saturation Transfer Magnetic Resonance Imaging. 9
- DP** Differential Privacy. 9
- ETL** Extraction, Transform and Load. 9
- GBNF** GGML Backus-Naur Form. 9, 23
- GED** Graph Edit Distance. 9, 24, 25
- GMM** Gaussian Mixture Models. 9
- GPT** Generative Pre-trained Transformer. 9, 42
- GUI** Graphical User Interface. 9
- HEREDITARY** HetERogeneous sEmantic Data integration for the guT-bRain interplaY. 3, 9, 10, 35, 45
- HERO** HEREDITARY Ontology. 9–11
- HMM** Hidden Markov Model. 9
- iDPP** Intelligent Disease Progression Prediction. 9
- IR** Information Retrieval. 9, 11, 12, 19, 21
- KG** Knowledge Graph. 3, 7, 9–12, 15–23, 25, 27–29, 35, 45
- LLM** Large Language Model. 9, 28, 43
- LM** Language Model. 9–12, 14, 16, 20–25, 27, 40–45
- MS** Multiple Sclerosis. 7, 9
- MWEM** Multiplicative Weights Exponential Mechanism. 9, 41
- NLIs** Natural Language Interface. 9, 41
- NLP** Natural Language Processing. 9–12, 21, 45
- OnSET** Ontology and Sparse data Exploration Tool. 7, 9–11, 13–16, 18–21, 25, 45
- OQL** Ontology Query Language. 9

PCA Principal Component Analysis. 9, 39, 42–44
PD Parkinson's Disease. 7, 9, 40, 44
PGO Performance-guided optimisation. 9
RAG Retrieval Augmented Generation. 9, 22
SUS System Usability Score. 9
TTYG Talk To Your Graph. 9, 10, 28, 45
UMAP Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection. 9
VA Visual Analytics. 9, 39, 40, 42, 44
WASM WebAssembly. 9

1 Introduction

Knowledge bases contain structured, typically large amounts of connected data and information, requiring tools to make them accessible. This also holds true for the medical domain, where KGs are used to fact-check claims, improve drug discovery, and aid professional in their choices (Peng et al., 2023). One such example of structured information can be found through the structuring of medical information within HEREDITARY, where Task 3.1 is concerned with constructing such a KG for medical records and relations, called HEREDITARY Ontology (HERO) (Menotti & Silvello, 2024). Another example is PubMed, where large amounts of medical research information is published by conferences, journals, and other forms of scientific outlets. Current machine learning approaches are capable of extracting structured information from these documents, e.g., in form of entities and relationships. We note supported by HEREDITARY (Task 5.6), the GutBrainIE@CLEF25 dataset aims to foster the development of Information Extraction (IE) systems that support experts by automatically extracting and linking knowledge from scientific literature about the gut-brain interplay, thereby enhancing the understanding of its role in neurological diseases, with a strong focus on Parkinson's disease. It is among others from these novel technologies, that we are faced with large KGs. These due to their size and topical breadth (basically any kind of information can be structured in a KG) pose a challenge for making use of them. This is in particular due to the need to retrieve, analyze, discover and re-use information from KGs.

Traditional approaches use query languages like SPARQL (Seaborne et al., 2024) or SQL (Affolter et al., 2019) to formulate the information needs using abstract and strict languages. Modern approaches have started to use Natural Language Processing (NLP) and visual approaches to improve accessibility for non-experts in these specialized languages (Affolter et al., 2019; Chau et al., 2008; S. Liu et al., 2024; Urchade et al., 2024; Vargas et al., 2019). In this deliverable we present the outcomes so far from HEREDITARY Task 5.3 (Visual querying and analytical interaction). Specifically, we present three novel querying methodologies each extending the capabilities for interactive retrieval. Two of these operate on KGs, and one operates on high-dimensional data sets, all of them supporting the interaction with data and obtaining insights in an interactive, query- and dialogue-driven way.

OnSet Our first tool, OnSET (Sections 2 and 3), integrates user guidance based on Language Models (LMs) into a framework for exploratory search. We show multiple case studies covered by the tool, both within HEREDITARY and further domains. The tool is first analyzed case-by-case to illustrate these use cases within specific information needs or scenarios. The tool is evaluated within the scope of the natural-language to visual prototype query pipeline by a synthetic evaluation pipeline.

Talk To Your Graph Our second tool is the Talk To Your Graph (TTYG) system (Section 4), where users can ask a chatbot questions about information contained within KGs. This system is built using LMs equipped with tool calls to retrieve data from external sources using LM-generated SPARQL queries.

Neurodegen-Vis Finally, we introduce the Neurodegen-Vis dashboard (Section 4), which is also LM-based, and allows users to gather insights into the distribution of patient data across various axes within the dataset. The dashboard combines traditional visualization systems for retrieved datasets with an explainability-focused chat interface. The chat interface can explain the included data columns based on their names and metadata; and allows the users to quickly change the visualization and selection of data. We, furthermore, only operate on anonymized data to preserve the confidentiality of the data.

Section 6 concludes and outlines next steps. Our set of toolkits highlights the variety of querying systems developed within HEREDITARY, and how they integrate into the various complimentary aspects of the project – from the structured knowledge and ontologies to privacy-preserving efforts and efficient visual retrieval.

2 OnSET Query Editor

The OnSET query editor has been developed to allow users to visually query the HERO and other ontologies and associated KGs. We employ concepts from user guidance, visual analytics, exploratory search, and Information Retrieval (IR) to arrive at a component integrating a wide variety of features to ease the creation of queries over ontologies.

2.1 Introduction

IR from KGs is typically performed using specialized languages, such as SPARQL (Gruber, 1995; Seaborne et al., 2024). These query languages, however, require specialized knowledge of both the syntactical nature of the query language and the schema of the KG. This additional barrier of entry can be challenging for non-experts of these languages and first-time users, hindering easy exploration of these rich knowledge bases, such as DBpedia (Lehmann et al., 2015). To further the use of ontologies and KGs by non-expert users, existing systems already provide natural language or visual interfaces, making these applications more accessible to them. We relate these works to ours in Section 2.2. Compared to existing systems, our system enhances the initial exploration phase of ontologies.

Our system, OnSET, combines the existing interface paradigms to foster approachable exploration of ontologies, providing visual query building features with novel aspects. OnSET incorporates concepts from user guidance, an approach to lead user towards their goals. Users might not even have a specific information need in mind, but still intend to explore the data (Pérez-Messina et al., 2023). OnSET facilitates this exploration of large ontologies while maintaining a user-friendly approach though these approaches. None of the related works consider the missing knowledge of users who may need guidance towards a first information need. We solve this initial guidance problem using topic modeling over the ontology, an approach originating from NLP. We furthermore extend the expansion of our prototype graph¹ with a semantic search interface that reduces the barrier of entry. This search interface enables users who do not possess knowledge of the ontology to nevertheless add specific new nodes and edges to the prototype graph by searching for related terms and connections. The users therefore only require semantic information derived from the topics presented initially. Furthermore, we expand the notion of dynamic results by providing instances of our prototype graph as small multiples, which can be inspected with further detail on demand. We utilize advances in NLP as the basis for the search and exploration capabilities within OnSET. Our application builds on open systems, starting with our SPARQL databases system qlever (Bast & Buchhold, 2017), over the topic modeling approach based on BERTopic (Grootendorst, 2022) and finally using open and efficient LMs (Kusupati et al., 2022; Teknium et al., 2024).

OnSET also includes facilities to foster the exploration of the query evolution. Other, related visual query builders (see Section 2.2.2) do not consider the *changes* and *evolution* of queries between different stages of information need, or differences in the result set. These attributes are commonly found in *exploratory search*, where the user seeks information driven by curiosity. The formulation of queries is often iteratively performed based on the results obtained from a starting query, as the final information goal may not be clearly defined at the beginning of the search (White & Roth, 2009). The differences between queries at the various stages can provide users with insights in the form of result set changes and awareness of how the query evolves (Krause et al., 2016). Our system makes use of the notion of *query differences* through difference views of the visual graph query building process. We present a novel interface that displays the changes made to the prototype

¹The term *example query* is used by related works (Lissandrini et al., 2020; Vargas et al., 2019) to describe their approach of providing an instance from the KG by connecting instances within the graph. In contrast, our query paradigm builds on the notion of a *prototype* graph, which defines the structural *prototype* and constraints, i.e. the blueprint of a graph. This information can then be used to search for within the KG, resulting in instances of the graph.

graph by the user in a single interface, in both the query and result views. Our system, furthermore, utilizes the difference features to incorporate change requests in natural language using a LM-based interface. Our novel query interface enables users to instruct the system to add or delete parts of the query graph. This system allows for input in natural language, which is matched to the ontology based on semantic similarity. This matching enables our system to be robust in the face of incomplete user knowledge about the ontology, and constrains the possible change sets to the limits imposed by the ontology.

2.2 Related Work

Existing retrieval systems already aim to reduce these barriers to entry. Some of these include natural language querying approaches (Ferré, 2016; Lei et al., 2018; Lissandrini et al., 2020), others build towards visual interfaces for building queries over knowledge bases (Clemmer & Davies, 2011; Francart, 2023; García et al., 2022; P. Liu et al., 2022; Vargas et al., 2019).

2.2.1 NLP Query Approaches

Natural language interfaces focus on the ease of use and adaption of users' information needs as text, or, to some extent, incorporate NLP concepts (Lei et al., 2018; Lissandrini et al., 2020). The *NLP Engine* (Lei et al., 2018) aims to convert any natural language query to a SPARQL query for further processing using multiple translational layers. The system focuses on query mappings and assumes some prior knowledge of the schema users within the data to formulate queries in natural language. *Graph Query Suggestion* (Lissandrini et al., 2020) expands the initial query graph of a user by suggesting related links using traditional IR approaches. Furthermore, they build on the notion of example graphs, where the user builds a graph that serves as an example or prototype to retrieve similar structures from the KG.

2.2.2 Visual Query Approaches

On the other hand, the visual querying approaches focus on providing approachable systems to facilitate the use of KGs for non-experts. *GRAPHITE* (Chau et al., 2008) and *VISAGE* (Pienta et al., 2016) both employ visual editing of the prototype graphs to foster the exploration of KGs with a focus on fuzzy matching, query suggestions, and fast retrieval times. *RDF Explorer* (Vargas et al., 2019) approaches this task by providing a graph editor, enabling the creation of graph examples to retrieve matching instances from the KG. The system provides users with query expansion options throughout the application, displaying dynamic results as queries are built. The authors relate their work to previous query builders, notably *Smeagol* (Clemmer & Davies, 2011). This alternative follows similar exploration and retrieval paradigms but does not offer a comparable number of SPARQL features. *KG VQL* (P. Liu et al., 2022) defines a novel visual query language to ease the transformation between the visual querying and result set, at the cost of disregarding explorative approaches, favoring the proposed transformation approach to convert between data examples and queries. *Rhizomer* (García et al., 2022) approaches the exploration of knowledge bases by providing different user interfaces to explore only at the top-level, graph-level, or only at the instance level of a single type. *Spar-natural* (Francart, 2023) simplifies many of these exploratory approaches into a tree-based approach that directly yields tabular results, thereby limiting easier result set exploration. Similarly, *SPARKLIS* (Ferré, 2016) approaches the topic by representing the query as a single natural language query expressed as a template over the ontology and combines the creation of the query with a small user interface system. Neither of these systems offers fuzzy search interfaces or initial user guidance to support novice users in their explorative search.

Figure 1: OnSET user flow. The user can select topics of interest and retrieve possible start links. These links are then expanded & constrained within an editor, which finally retrieves different instances of the searched graph.

2.2.3 Graph Difference Views

Showing the differences and similarities between graphs – i.e., visual graph comparison – has also been subject to various studies (Beck et al., 2017). For example, there are approaches to illustrate the partial similarities between two graphs by identifying common subgraphs. Such can be merged by determining node positions which do not change (much), creating a (super) graph (Diehl et al., 2001). Alternatively, they can be displayed side-by-side, with a third view showing local similarities in a tripartite multi-view system (Andrews et al., 2009). There are also approaches for weighted graphs, which illustrate the differences in edge weights through a visual encoding of the respective edges (Alper et al., 2013). Also relevant to our design are approaches for comparing an arbitrary number of (relatively similar) graphs. Such can be achieved, e.g., by showing their connectives in a small multiples visualization (Behrisch et al., 2013), or by stacking the planar graphs in a third dimension, thus giving a 2.5-dimensional view (Brandes et al., 2004). Another approach, *EditLens*, utilizes a lens system to show changes performed on a larger graph (Gladisch et al., 2014).

As we are dealing with progressive graphs, we rely on highlighting through color to indicate changes. Our system, furthermore, operates on smaller sub-graphs and within a novel domain, query graphs, and applies the concept to exploratory search.

2.3 Methodology

2.3.2 Graph Definition

OnSET builds upon the notion of a prototypical graph $G_p := (N_p, E_p)$ that serves as the blueprint for all retrieved instances. This graph representation is similar to BGP (Hogan et al., 2021), a system to express simple graph patterns for queries over KGs. Our definition extends this by adhering to the schema imposed by the ontology. The sub-graph G_{proto} of the ontology consists of the nodes N_{proto} , each one an instance of the classes \mathcal{C} , and edges E_{proto} , each one a link of link types \mathcal{L} . The multiset of nodes can contain a class multiple times, and a link can only span the allowed end and start types (within the class hierarchy), i.e.

$$N_{proto} := \{n_1, \dots, n_m\} \subseteq \mathcal{C},$$

$$E_{proto} \subseteq \{e_i = (n_t, l_j, n_h) \mid \text{subtypeof}(n_t, \text{fromtype}(l_j)), \\ \text{subtypeof}(n_h, \text{totype}(l_j))\} \subseteq (N_p \times \mathcal{L} \times N_p).$$

Each node can be extended using additional sub-queries related to the node's classes properties $p \in \mathcal{P}_{N_{proto}}$, which can be either constraints $\text{constraint}(p, \text{cond.})$ or property values $\text{value}(p)$

$$S_{N_{proto}} := \{s_1, \dots\} \subseteq \text{constraint}(\mathcal{P}_{N_{proto}}, \text{cond.}) \cup \text{value}(\mathcal{P}_{N_{proto}}, \text{cond.})$$

The resulting instance graphs are queried from the database by constructing the SPARQL from the class, link, and sub-query constraint sets and retrieving the results.

2.3.3 Difference Graphs

To construct the difference between graphs, we take two graphs, $G_{proto,l}$ and $G_{proto,r}$, and construct the set differences, which will yield the additions and removals of nodes. We compare the individual nodes and constraints by serial numerical identifiers, while the result graphs are compared using their connected instance nodes.

The added and deleted multiset are therefore constructed by comparing the identifiers, i.e.

$$N_{proto,add} := \{n_{proto,r} \in N_{proto,r} \mid \\ \text{id}(n_{proto,r}) \notin \{\text{id}(n_{proto,l}), n_{proto,l} \in N_{proto,l}\}\}$$

$$N_{proto,del} := \{n_{proto,l} \in N_{proto,l} \mid \\ \text{id}(n_{proto,l}) \notin \{\text{id}(n_{proto,r}), n_{proto,r} \in N_{proto,r}\}\}$$

$$N_{proto,shared} := \{n_{proto,l} \in N_{proto,l} \mid \\ \text{id}(n_{proto,l}) \in \{\text{id}(n_{proto,r}), n_{proto,r} \in N_{proto,r}\}\}.$$

Similarly, the added and deleted sets of the sub-queries can be constructed using similar operations performed on the unchanged nodes $N_{proto,shared}$, i.e.

$$S_{N_{proto,shared},add} := \{s_{proto,r} \in S_{N_{proto,shared},r} \mid \\ \text{id}(s_{proto,r}) \notin \{\text{id}(s_{proto,l}), s_{proto,l} \in S_{N_{proto,l}}\}\}$$

$$S_{N_{proto,shared},del} := \{s_{proto,l} \in S_{N_{proto,shared},l} \mid \\ \text{id}(s_{proto,l}) \notin \{\text{id}(s_{proto,r}), s_{proto,r} \in S_{N_{proto,r}}\}\}.$$

These difference sets are then displayed directly within the query view if the user is tracking their changes, and updated dynamically. We highlight the added nodes in green, and the deleted ones in red²

²We offer a colorblind mode to aid users with Red-Green color blindness.

2.3.4 Automatic Result Set Overview

To enable a more in-depth result overview, we provide value-wise fetching of node attributes using the sub-query elements mentioned above. The user may be searching for the ages of patients who have a diagnosis of a specific disease and wants to know the distribution of these dates, as there might be hundreds of patients. The result set overview enables a quick visualization of the attributes of the nodes within the graph using standard techniques for common data types. We employ a heuristic to select the most suitable visualization type based on the current setting. If the user chooses only one value, we show the feature distribution. If the feature is continuous we group it into a set number of buckets, if it is discrete we show the most common discrete types, as shown in Figure 4a. Furthermore, if the user chooses two value attributes, we either display a heatmap if there are too many data points or use a scatter plot to show the distribution of the results. For the patients example, the system would choose the histogram plot. We integrate these result set charts with our difference view by comparing the different result sets of the two prototype graphs, as long as the values selected to be retrieved still match. These could be the birthdate distributions of a specific disease compared to the overall distribution for our example. We also allow users to download difference sets to apply their own statistical and visual evaluations outside our system, provided they are satisfied with the information from our queries.

2.3.5 Integration of a Natural Language Query System

We utilize the difference views to manage the integration of a LM-based query feature, allowing users to view the possible changes the LM would make based on a natural language query before accepting or rejecting them. This is especially helpful if the LM makes a mistake by suggesting the wrong links or hallucination (Ji et al., 2023). Other failure cases include an information need by the user that the KG cannot satisfy, but the user specified in their query. The assistance system may still return some changes that are loosely related to the user request, but the user can still modify them before accepting the changes. The query parsing to a structured change set follows the same architecture which we outline in Section 3. The change set is then applied to the prototype graph G_p , and the difference view is automatically activated, including a first initial difference calculation according to the schema outlined above.

2.3.6 User Interface

The resulting prototype graph ((a) in Figure 3) is then utilized in three ways, similar to the levels of García et al. (2022), but integrated into the core retrieval process. First, the graph is used on top of a 3D circle-packing visualization of the ontology to illustrate how the classes are distributed over the ontology with respect to its class hierarchy (c). Second, the prototype graph is used to generate a SPARQL query to retrieve the intended instance set. This instance set populates the third use case of the graph, where we show small instances of the initial prototype graph (b). These instances, or result sets, can then be inspected, and the properties of the retrieved instances can be explored individually. The presentation of smaller, visually similar instances also differentiates our system from existing approaches, as we visually relate the result set and prototype graph.

2.4 Implementation

The outlined concepts are integrated into our system, OnSET, focusing on fast user responses even on larger ontologies. We furthermore base our entire stack on open-source systems, allowing institutions or users to

Figure 3: The query can be built using a straightforward interactive process. The user can add any allowed link within the ontology, with a visual indication of its prevalence within the KG shown by the link width. Users can also add constraints to the nodes. (a) The tool immediately provides visual results (b) and provides a visual indicator of the explored classes and links using a small three-dimensional circle packing “minimap” in the bottom center (c).

start and tweak their local systems. We show the implementation of our user guidance in Figure 2, the query builder in Figure 3, and the difference views in Figures 4 and 5

To achieve our first goal of fast user responses, we only compute the topic modeling and embeddings of links and classes on the first startup with a specific ontology. We store our resulting hierarchical topic map and embeddings in PostgreSQL³ with the help of the pgvector extension⁴, which enables fast retrieval given a query embedding. To generate these embeddings quickly, even on commodity hardware, we use the stella_en_400M_v5⁵ model, which is, at the time of submission, the best-performing smaller model w.r.t. the massive text embedding benchmark (Muennighoff et al., 2022). The precomputed topics are generated using the same embedding model, and additional topic labels are generated using the Hermes Llama 3.2 8B model (Teknum et al., 2024).

While these efforts improve the query time for building the prototype graph, live updates of the result set require a similarly fast system. To achieve those fast responses, even on more complex queries and on commodity hardware, we use qler (Bast & Buchhold, 2017), a SPARQL query engine that outperforms most existing engines in both speed and system requirements. This speedup enables our system to serve and display updates as the user builds their query, aiding the user in retrieving non-empty sets and showing intermediate results to guide the search even further.

Our user interface builds on Vue.js⁶, in combination with three.js⁷ and D3.js (Bostock et al., 2011). All the used database systems and models are open-source and open-weight, providing state-of-the-art performance

³<https://www.postgresql.org/>

⁴<https://github.com/pgvector/pgvector>

⁵https://huggingface.co/NovaSearch/stella_en_400M_v5

⁶<https://vuejs.org/>

⁷<https://threejs.org/>

Figure 4: Difference graph examples for the DBpedia ontology.

in their respective fields while still being able to run on commodity hardware.

2.5 Case study

We present OnSET in the scope of two case studies for explorative search over two different ontologies. First, we show how a novice user might start their exploration of DBpedia (Lehmann et al., 2015) to discover interesting facts and relations. Our second use case covers the BTO (Faggioli, Menotti, et al., 2024) and how experts within a field might approach more specialized ontologies.

Exploring DBpedia DBpedia (Lehmann et al., 2015) is a curated ontology and KG derived from Wikipedia, providing general linked information. Querying and exploring this knowledge base typically requires the use of the SPARQL language. Our visual exploration toolkit, OnSET, enables the novice user to start exploring the knowledge base immediately through the presented topics.

An example of such an exploration flow could be the initial selection of the topic “Broadcasting system information” and “Athlete rankings and achievements”, as seen in Figure 2a. This selection queries our system for links similar to the selected topic and displays start link suggestions to the user. The user can, therefore, start exploring DBpedia without prior knowledge of the classes and links contained in it, hinting the user at possible links within the ontology. Next, the user selects a link from the suggested list, initiating the process of building the prototype graph. The user then adds links and constraints to the prototype graph, drilling down towards a specific result set of interest—in this case, persons who trained an athlete and presented a television show, and where they were educated. OnSET guides the user towards non-empty sets by indicating prevalence in the KG through link strength. The user can assume that the result set is not empty due to the strong links between all classes on the prototype graph, which can be immediately verified as the result set is updated directly. While building the graph, the “minimap” in the bottom of Figure 3 is dynamically updated to indicate which regions within the class hierarchy are covered. In this case, two links span the class hierarchy while one link, the athlete’s trainer, covers only the local hierarchy within the person region.

The difference views of our querying system offer additional avenues in exploratory search, which we show in further examples. In Figure 4a, the user first searches for opening themes of television shows that are recorded in any popular place. They select the runtime in seconds to be plotted. The users, however, decide to contrast this initial information without the opening theme constraint and add the constraint “York” to the label of the populated place. Our interface displays this shift, first, by marking the added nodes in green and the deleted parts in red, with additional indications in the borders of the nodes. The second change is the difference view in the result distribution, showing how the runtime compares between the queries. The users

Figure 5: The BTO KG queried using the difference view to explore the relationship between different semantic attributes.

could observe that there are many more results for the second query, and that the opening themes have, on average, a shorter runtime.

We also consider smaller result sets, where the query might be more specific and the result relations are of interest. For this use, we provide different views in the instance result view, showing individual instances of the result graph to the user. We again calculate the difference across all results and highlight added and removed instances. In this case, the user queries for persons who are both authors of a work and gold medalists in a sports event, as shown in Figure 4b. There are, naturally, only a few instances of this particular relation within the graph, and the user may be interested in the specific works by Olympians who participated in the games of the 2000s, adding a label constraint. We show the user the difference in the result set, emphasizing how the result set might have reduced in size due to the additional constraint.

Exploring BTO Our second example outlines the exploratory search over the BTO (Faggioli, Menotti, et al., 2024), an ontology and KG that contains semantic knowledge about patients, caregivers, and their diagnoses. The explorative process for an interested party starts similarly to the use case above, but is presented with different topics.

The user might be interested in diseases associated with certain demographics, so they start their search with the topic “Patient demographics and health status” and “Diseases and Disorders”, starting with the node “Patient” as shown in Figure 2a. This single node is too general, so they search for “test”, as seen in Figure 2b. Using the semantic search capabilities, they find the relation “enrolledIn” within the ontology and add them to their prototype graph. Nevertheless, this relatively small prototype graph allows the user to compare and search over these links of interest in the result set.

2.6 Conclusion

The presented IR system, OnSET, allows novice users without any prior information about the knowledge base to build queries and explore it in an integrated manner. We first present related systems that share a similar aim of enabling non-expert users to construct SPARQL queries and explore KGs. Our approach, however, differs in that we utilize initial guidance approaches to lower the barrier of entry even further by providing semantic search for both the initial link search and the prototype graph expansion, and ultimately, immediate result feedback is built right into the interface. We also provide an overview of the ontology to help relate the current query to the entire ontology.

We emphasize the use of specialized open database systems to provide fast response times, enabling interactive and immediate result exploration, even for minor changes to the prototype graph. We finally demonstrate two possible explorative user flows using OnSET to inspire further use cases. The system, furthermore, includes a novel difference view for graph query building that allows users to explore the evolution of their graph query in an integrated view with the prototype graph, constraints, and result sets. We also integrate a LM interface to facilitate exploration with little prior knowledge of the graph and the user interface, leveraging semantic retrieval and fuzzy matching to the strict ontology structure. We allow, through the difference implementation, reversal of the changes to reduce the effect of invalid modifications by the LM, and more experimental searches by the users.

The resulting tools enable non-expert users to explore relations of interest within the KG, including the dependencies of attributes within the queried sub-graph. Our difference views, specifically, foster the understanding of differences of sub-graphs and their attributes and distributions over the whole result set. This effect in distributional change is especially evident for the change in attribute filters, which we demonstrate through several case studies on different ontologies and KGs, the DBpedia and BTO. While the DBpedia use cases demonstrate how our system informs users in exploratory use cases, the BTO illustrates the applicability of our tool to experts in their respective fields. They can build example graphs and query for distributional changes in medical disease attributes, exploring these differences within our tool.

2.7 Future Work

OnSET provides a low barrier of entry for novice users to KG exploration. We intend to expand the breadth of queries that users can express through our system in the future. A current limitation of our system is the inability to specify complete graphs, as the user can, for the time being, only build tree-like graphs, while closed graphs might be of interest for more advanced or intricate use cases.

We intend to refine the constraint application process as the filtering strength of the properties of an instance is not yet clearly visually defined. This refinement could aid the user in exploring and retrieving data more attuned to their need and assist in non-empty result retrieval. Another interesting avenue is the extension towards optional parts of the prototype graph, both in the form of links and constraints, to facilitate more fuzzy retrieval. Another missing aspect of the constraint-building process is the consideration of missing properties, where a search over multimodal data types, such as spatial or image data, could be interesting.

3 Graph Queries from Natural Language using Constrained Language Models & Evaluation

We extend the OnSET system with another aspect on the intersection of IR and NLP, extracting prototype graphs from natural language queries and integrating these into our query editor.

3.1 Introduction

Ontologies are usually queried using specialized query languages, such as SPARQL (Seaborne et al., 2024), which can pose an additional barrier of entry for users seeking to retrieve structured knowledge from such systems. This chapter, therefore, proposes a novel querying strategy, which maps relational queries in natural language to prototype graph representations, which can then be further adjusted by the user to desired retrieval criteria. The system is tuned for natural language queries formulated as relations, differing from traditional opaque question-answering approaches, which typically do not visualize the generated queries or their processing, nor allow edits to the query.

Our system extracts the prototype graph structure from the query using the capabilities of LMs to extract information from natural language input – even in cases where there is no exact match for the required information within the ontology. We achieve a valid prototype graph by constraining the LM output using a dynamically created grammar to adhere to the classes and links present within the ontology. This novel addition of the grammar to the query generation by the LM enables our system, in turn, to always return prototype graphs that are valid within the context of the used ontology. Our system, furthermore, allows the user to refine and adjust the prototype graph in a visual editor, enabling the correction of mistakes the LM might make. Within this editor, the users can improve their queries or extend them towards more complex queries, enabling users to edit their queries without modifying the SPARQL query or any other intermediate representation.

We evaluate the prototype graph extraction performance of our approach using a synthetic benchmark, consisting of sampled sub-graphs and corresponding LM-generated natural language queries. This synthetic benchmark is tested for alignment with human query examples using our synthetic query generation framework. Our retrieval approach, furthermore, does not require any metadata about the ontologies or query examples, unlike other systems (Emonet et al., 2024).

3.2 Related Work

Previous efforts to map queries presented in natural language towards complex, constrained query languages (Emonet et al., 2024; Ferré, 2016; Lei et al., 2018) focused on retrieving and generating SPARQL queries directly, resulting in either very complex systems or retrieval with many iterative refinement steps.

(Lei et al., 2018) map a natural language query onto a particular, tailored, *Ontology Query Language*, used as an intermediate representation, and then converted to SQL. They use the ontology to find relevant terms in the natural language query and map them to elements of the ontology. This approach limits the output to specific instances, hindering both extensibility and exploration. *SPARKLIS* (Ferré, 2016) approaches the mapping from natural language to a SPARQL query through a mixture of highly constrained natural language and visual exploration. The constraints placed upon the queries help to adhere to the graph schema but could hinder more straightforward exploration.

More typically, KGs are queried using SPARQL (Seaborne et al., 2024), which can be generated with LMs (Emonet et al., 2024; S. Liu et al., 2024; Meyer et al., 2024). (Meyer et al., 2024) have shown that the out-of-the-box performance of multiple proprietary LMs is lacking for direct generation of SPARQL queries

Figure 6: Our query extraction process using LMs, using the query example “a person and the child of a person have the alma mater of the same university”. We transform the natural language query into a prototype graph using a constrained LM. The graph is first approximated using a LM (a), where the generated classes and links might not match the ontology yet. This initial guess of the LM is used to search for semantically similar relations (b). With the subset of all possible links and nodes, the graph is extracted again and corrected for possible errors (c), resulting in a graph that adheres to the ontology. The resulting graph can be edited (d), e.g. an additional constraint for a country can be added. The resulting prototype graph can be used to perform queries over a KG to retrieve instances (e).

from natural language queries. They demonstrate that adding the ontology, in textual representation, to the query enhances the generation. The generation is further improved if only relevant classes and relations are provided. Similarly, Emonet et al. (Emonet et al., 2024) improve upon these results by targeting large-scale federated KGs. They develop a Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) system that automatically augments the LM input with relevant ontology classes and manually created example queries. Finally, Liu et al. (S. Liu et al., 2024) introduce SPINACH, a question-answering LM agent for Wikidata, that iteratively performs actions: searching Wikidata for entities, properties, or example queries, and executing SPARQL queries on demand. Effectively, these methods highlight that incorporating the ontology is essential to improve generated SPARQL queries. Nevertheless, these methods require the LMs to generate a syntactically and semantically correct SPARQL query, but—due to syntax errors or hallucination of properties—can require feedback error messages to fix the query iteratively.

In comparison to these works, our method utilizes the ontology to constrain the LM output, thereby creating a prototype graph that can be directly mapped to a valid SPARQL query. This intermediate graph eliminates syntax errors and hallucinations while enabling the usage of smaller models ($\leq 8B$ parameters) and removing the need for feedback error messages. The system is also robust against semantic mismatches between the query and schema, allowing users to formulate their queries more freely. We also seamlessly integrate this natural language querying system with a visual interface, enabling users to adjust and refine their query after the mapping phase has been completed.

3.3 Methodology

Our KG retrieval approach builds on the notion of graph extraction and graph instance retrieval. To realize this notion, we require the graph extraction from natural language as outlined in Figure 6. The graph extraction performance is evaluated using a synthetic dataset, generated with our query generation pipeline. The synthetic dataset is shown to be representative of real results through a comparison of using both synthetic and human-written queries on a subset of queries.

3.3.1 Graph Extraction

Our KG retrieval system builds upon the notion of a prototype graph $G_p := (N_p, E_p)$ from Section 2.3.2. Our graph extraction pipeline from the natural language returns this prototype graph using a multistep approach illustrated in Figure 6. This approach first extracts an unconstrained graph G_p'' from the natural language prompt using the structured output of a LM (M. X. Liu et al., 2024), which serves as the basis for retrieval of semantically similar and existing classes \mathcal{C} and links \mathcal{L} . These are then used to perform another round of structured generation to get G_p' , which is refined to the final prototype graph G_p that can be used to retrieve instance graphs $G_{I,h}$.

Graph from Natural Language This first unconstrained graph generation step is required as the basis for further querying of possible classes \mathcal{C} and links \mathcal{L} . The LM output is nevertheless restrained to return only a specific JSON schema through GGML Backus-Naur Form (GBNF) (M. X. Liu et al., 2024; llama.cpp authors, 2025). This measure enforces a consistent output that can be parsed and used for further processing. These constraints allow us to construct the intermediate graph G_p'' , which has no constraints regarding the ontology, i.e., \mathcal{L} and \mathcal{C} are open. While we could constrain the graph types to the whole ontology at this step, we have no way to enforce the structural correctness of the graph over the outgoing link types, increasing the probability of an invalid graph.

Constraints from Graph The unconstrained graph is used to retrieve candidates for the next generation step. This retrieval is performed for each node $n_i \in N_p$ and edge $e_j \in E_p$ using sentence embeddings of the node and link description. These embeddings are used to retrieve the top k most similar results in terms of cosine distance from all classes \mathcal{C} and links \mathcal{L} . The LM generation is then further constrained to only include these results. This retrieval of semantically similar links results in the subset of classes $\mathcal{C}' \subseteq \mathcal{C}$ and links $\mathcal{L}' \subseteq \mathcal{L}$.

Constrained Graph from Natural Language Finally, the prototype graph G_p is generated by providing the LM with the same instruction as in the first step, but with additional constraints placed upon the output generation through GBNF (llama.cpp authors, 2025). These use the additional information of the possible candidate classes \mathcal{C}' and links \mathcal{L}' from the previous step. This limited set of only semantically similar classes enables the LM still to express any graph from the natural language query while adhering to the relevant query constraints. The LM-generated graph G_p' may contain invalid or flipped links as we cannot enforce a valid graph structure on the output. This problem is mitigated by the previous step of only using the ontology subsets and by cleaning the graph using two rules. The first one exchanges the direction of the edge, essentially swapping the nodes $(n_t, l_j, n_h) \mapsto (n_h, l_j, n_t)$, if the types are flipped, i.e., the link l_j may not go from n_t to n_h , but from n_h to n_t . Our second rule discards any invalid links from the graph if they violate the type constraints.

3.3.2 Synthetic Evaluation Methodology

The described graph retrieval system is evaluated using synthetically generated queries from a sampled prototype graph $G_{p,s}$. This graph is used to generate queries in natural language using either a LM that is prompted with the graph as input structure or a template-based query generation. We additionally validate our query generation methodology against queries generated by humans by comparing the resulting evaluation metrics. The natural language prompt is, in turn, used to extract the prototype graph G_p using the method from above. Finally, the sampled and extracted graphs are compared and evaluated for similarity. This evaluation

system does not incorporate user refinements for adjusting the output graph, as the methodology evaluates only the directly returned prototype graph G_p .

Graph Sampling The first step in our synthetic evaluation pipeline is the sampling of prototype graphs $G_{p,s}$ from the ontology. The sampling is based on probabilities derived from the instance counts of the links. We additionally select classes that are lower in the class hierarchy using a similar probabilistic approach. Finally, further links are added based on a random choice of node and a similar probabilistic selection.

Generation of the Query Next, the natural language query is generated synthetically from the previously sampled graph $G_{p,s}$ using a LM, more specifically the Hermes 3 Llama 3.2 3B model (Teknum et al., 2024). The LM is presented with a textual representation of the types of classes and links within the graph and prompted, using a one-shot approach, to generate the queries. We also employ a template-based query generation approach to prevent potential information leaks and evaluate simpler queries (Sannigrahi et al., 2024). Additionally, we create 12 human-written queries from the sampled graphs to validate our evaluation methodologies for queries used in practice.

Scoring the Graphs Finally, the prototype graph G_p can be extracted from the synthetic query using our graph extraction methodology and compared to the ground truth sampled graph $G_{p,s}$. This evaluation employed two scoring methodologies: one for the retrieval performance of the nodes N_p and relations E_p , and another for the graph layout. First, the similarity between the retrieved nodes N_p and sampled nodes $N_{p,s}$ is compared using the F_1 -score over the sets. This set-based $F_{1,node}$ -score uses the true positives $TP = |N_p \cap N_{p,s}|$, false positives $FP = |N_p - N_{p,s}|$ and false negatives $FN = |N_{p,s} - N_p|$ rates from set intersections and differences. The $F_{1,rel}$ of the relations is computed using the same scheme using E_p and $E_{p,s}$.

Second, the graph similarity is computed using the Graph Edit Distance (GED) (Abu-Aisheh et al., 2015), which employs a stricter notion of similarity, requiring not only isomorphism between the graphs but also the same node and link types for the graphs. To achieve a comparable score to the F_1 scores and between different graph sizes, we weigh the distance by the number of nodes and links and invert it, giving the normalized GED score

$$GED_s = 1 - \frac{GED}{\max\{|N_p|, |N_{p,s}|\} + \max\{|E_p|, |E_{p,s}|\}}$$

Both evaluation methodologies provide scores for a single query example. We therefore reduce them to single values by averaging the scores over the different queries and evaluation settings.

3.3.3 Constraining the LM

The LMs are constrained to a schema specified to a grammar whenever we retrieve any graph using language generation. To this end, we use llama-cpp-agent⁸, which can constrain the LM to only output a specific model using a predefined grammar. The first prototype graph G_p'' uses a static schema and grammar. In the second generation step, the grammar is adapted to the specific, similar relations found utilizing the output of the first round. The updated grammar is then used to constrain the output only to contain valid types and links, which can be used to generate the correct prototype graph G_p . The graph G_p can be converted into a SPARQL query if the user requires it for further use.

⁸<https://llama-cpp-agent.readthedocs.io/>

Evaluated Models and Ontologies The evaluation of this work relies heavily on the use of LMs for graph retrieval, semantic retrieval, and constrained retrieval. We use the Hermes models (Teknium et al., 2024) (3B, 8B, and 70B parameter sizes) for generative retrieval tasks due to their fine-tuned capabilities for structured output, comparing them to two Qwen2.5 (32B parameters) models (Instruct and Code fine-tuned) (Qwen et al., 2025). A sentence-transformers model (Reimers & Gurevych, 2019) is used for all semantic retrieval tasks⁹.

We evaluate our approach on two ontologies, specifically

- DBpedia (Lehmann et al., 2015), an ontology and KG containing mapped information from Wikidata with 768 classes and 4,233,000 instances;
- BTO (Faggioli, Marchesin, et al., 2024), a smaller ontology and KG focusing on brain-related diseases; and

3.3.4 User Interface Integration

Additionally, we allow the users to refine their initial queries using our node-based editor OnSET, where links and nodes can be added to or removed from the graph, all within the constrained link set \mathcal{L} , and class set \mathcal{C} . This refinement can be helpful if our pipeline fails to find the correct graph or if the users want to refine their search without an additional text prompt.

Furthermore, we transparently display how the queries are built using the LM through a similar flow to that shown in Figure 6. This visualization should hold our system accountable for any mistakes and errors that occur during processing and may guide the user towards specifying more precise queries or exploring other querying avenues.

3.4 Results

We demonstrate our system’s capabilities to retrieve the correct graph from the query using our synthetic graph generation and evaluation pipeline. We evaluate the system at three different node sample counts, $k \in \{2, 3, 5, 7\}$, to model varying degrees of complexity in the queries. Each node sample count k is sampled for 128 synthetic queries. Additionally, we use four different open-weight models to test the dependence on model size and type. Our evaluation in Figure 7 shows that we can faithfully recover the prototype graph from the natural language query. While we cannot achieve a perfect recovery of all nodes and relations in all settings, we accomplish a F_1 score on the node retrieval on DBpedia across all models of approximately 0.7 throughout the different levels of complexity. The correct relations are retrieved at an even higher F_1 score of roughly 0.8 for the various ontologies and settings. Similarly, the GED score GED_s shows that the graph structure can be recovered quite well for most of the smaller graph sizes and drops only for the larger, more complex queries, demonstrating that our approach is most useful for smaller graphs. Our evaluation, furthermore, shows that using a larger model is only slightly beneficial for our use case. The system performs similarly across all model sizes and types, suggesting that even smaller models can reconstruct the prototype graph quite well due to the constraints we place on the output.

Our evaluation, furthermore, shows that the constraint and alignment step to the ontology, including our corrections, is essential to retrieve the correct graph as almost all combinations of query complexity, model, and ontology have a higher score after applying the constraint compared to the direct output of the model without the constraints of the ontology (reflected in the “raw” results).

Finally, we compare our different query generation methods in Table 1 by evaluating two query complexities $k = \{3, 5\}$ and comparing the scores. The LM-based generation method performs similarly to the

⁹We use the Stella 400M model (Zhang et al., 2025) for a great balance of model size and performance.

Figure 7: $F_{1,node}$, $F_{1,rel}$, and GED_s on two different ontologies, comparing different models and node amounts k , and the raw and aligned (constrained) output.

Table 1: Comparison of query generation methods for Hermes 3B on DBpedia with one shot prompts.

k	Query Origin	Stage	Mean $F_{1,node}$	Mean GED_s
3	human	aligned	0.63	0.40
		raw	0.52	0.24
	llama	aligned	0.71	0.46
		raw	0.68	0.36
templated	aligned	0.81	0.57	
	raw	0.79	0.54	
5	human	aligned	0.69	0.22
		raw	0.90	0.27
	llama	aligned	0.66	0.34
		raw	0.67	0.25
templated	aligned	0.83	0.48	
	raw	0.74	0.45	

human-generated queries. This comparative evaluation, additionally, shows that the template queries perform better than the compared LM-generated ones. These results indicate that the LMs perform better with simpler formatted queries, such as the template-generated queries.

3.5 Conclusion

We introduce a novel querying system to aid users in exploring ontologies and generating queries from natural language. The interface uses only natural language as the input, providing the users with a fuzzy interface to explore an otherwise strict system of classes and links. We achieve this translation from fuzzy input to the strict notion using a query processing pipeline that heavily utilizes LMs for generating the prototype graph, performing semantic similarity search, and constrained graph generation. We provide a prototype graph as an intermediate output from this pipeline. This prototype graph can be refined through a node-based editor to better reflect the users' information needs if the LM failed to map the natural language query completely or the user has a more specific information need.

We evaluate our system on a set of synthetic queries with varying levels of complexity. These should reflect users' varying information needs and queries while evaluating our system for more complex tasks. This evaluation demonstrates that the extracted prototype graphs accurately represent the sampled graphs, particularly for smaller graphs. This performance level, especially at the smaller graph sizes, should provide a robust system that adheres to the users' initial interests. We demonstrate that this level of performance can be achieved with smaller models.

In contrast, existing systems struggle with these smaller models and require significantly more powerful, and thus more expensive, models. They, furthermore, often require iterative systems to retrieve syntactically correct queries, whereas our system can provide valid queries using our two-step retrieval process. We furthermore validate our approach by comparing the synthetic queries generated by a LM and template system from the sampled graphs to a small set of manually written queries. These evaluations show that the LM-generated queries do indeed adhere to the manually written queries, thereby strengthening our query evaluation approach.

3.6 Future Work

The introduced system builds a prototype graph based on natural language input, enabling users to explore and query KGs effectively. Future versions could, however, enhance the robustness of retrieving the prototype graph from natural language queries for larger and more complex queries by utilizing more sophisticated models or fine-tuning smaller, more specialized models for the graph retrieval task at hand, thereby achieving even more precise initial graph responses. The fine-tuning of the models could even be performed directly on our synthetic query dataset.

Another avenue for further improvement in this system is the addition of constraints to the graph generated by the LMs. While we can constrain the properties (e.g. the age, name, or height of a person) within the user interface, we do not provide a way for the LM to add this to the generated query. These, however, are an integral part of the KG and the information they contain. We intend to extend the LM output and graph to include these filters on the edges and formalize these structures to get a constrained output, including these constraints.

4 Talk to Your Graph: Natural Language Querying of Neuro Degenerative Diseases

4.1 Introduction

Natural language querying (NLQ) and visual querying (VQ) are related as user-friendly paradigms for interacting with a KG, each mapping intuitive user input (language or visuals) to the same semantic graph model. The proposed approach Talk To Your Graph (TTYG) overcomes the need for SPARQL query writing and any knowledge about the technologies and particular semantic model and ontologies. This approach lowers barriers for end-users allowing them to use plain natural language (like English, or other languages) removing the need to learn technical languages like SPARQL. This approach transforms the way users interact with KGs, it fosters intuitive complex data interactions, and makes them schema-agnostic and stable on further changes in the KG structure.

4.2 Related Work

Current research explores the application of Large Language Models (LLMs) for NLQ of RDF KGs. Perevalov and Both (Both & Perevalov, 2024) demonstrate LLMs' effectiveness in verbalizing SPARQL queries across multiple languages, enhancing query understanding for non-experts. Avila et al. (Avila et al., 2024) introduce Auto-KGQA, an LLM-based framework for translating natural language questions to SPARQL queries and generating responses. Arazzi et al. (Arazzi et al., 2025) present SparqLLM, a Retrieval-Augmented Generation solution that combines template-based methods with LLMs to enhance query accuracy and visualization. Ongris et al. (Ongris et al., 2024) propose a GraphRAG system using LLM chaining for Wikidata querying, achieving improved SPARQL query generation by incorporating broader property candidates. While these approaches show promise in bridging the gap between natural language and structured data querying, challenges remain, including context window limitations and hallucination issues (Ongris et al., 2024). Additionally, research suggests that using controlled natural languages as intermediaries between natural language queries and formal query languages can reduce training data requirements for LLM-based semantic parsing in KG question answering systems (Lehmann et al., 2023). Recently are developed successful applications of NLQ for various domains: finance, industry, scholarly KGs (Jia et al., 2024). In biomedical domain the automatic KG construction from biomedical texts and proposed LLM based approaches for interaction with KGs foster clinical decision making and knowledge discovery (Jadhav et al., 2025). Overall, these studies highlight the potential of LLMs in making KG querying more accessible to non-expert users.

4.3 Data

The dataset used for this study is a subgraph BioGraphTalk of Target Discovery KG, which is built based on open data sets from Ontotext LinkedLifeData Inventory (LLDI)¹⁰. LLDI (see Figure 8) is a comprehensive solution that offers integrated, semantically enriched biomedical and healthcare data into single linked KG. It comprises from more than 200 public biomedical datasets in genomics, proteomics, pharma, clinical trials, metabolomics, diseases, biomedical scientific publications and more. Using semantic technologies and ontologies (like MeSH, SNOMED, and UMLS), it enables unified access, advanced querying, and knowledge discovery across life sciences data silos. The Inventory supports pharmaceutical research, drug discovery, and healthcare analytics by enhancing data harmonization, interoperability, and machine-readable insights.

¹⁰<https://www.ontotext.com/solutions/healthcare-and-life-sciences/linked-life-data-inventory/>

Figure 8: A data inventory organized as a map of data domains

GraphDB

Welcome to GraphDB

GraphDB is a graph database compliant with RDF and SPARQL specifications. It supports open APIs based on the RDF4J project and enables fast publishing of linked data on the web. The Workbench is used for searching, exploring and managing GraphDB repositories.

Run our interactive guides for an easy way into learning some basic concepts and getting started with GraphDB.

You can always come back to this panel by pressing the GraphDB icon in the top left corner.

Hide panel | Take me to the guides

1 2 3 4 5

View resource

Search RDF resources...
Hint: "abc" matches "abc", "ab-c" and "ab-c"

Active repository

Local
BioGraphTalk · Talk to you Life Sciences graph

total statements: 141,317,128
54,892,804 explicit
86,424,324 inferred
2.57 expansion ratio

Import RDF data | Export RDF data

Saved SPARQL queries

Add statements PREFIX dc: <http://purl.org/dc/elements-...>	ChEMBL: Which compounds affect s... PREFIX cco: <http://rdf.ebi.ac.uk/terms-...>
ChEMBL: Which compounds affect s... PREFIX cco: <http://rdf.ebi.ac.uk/terms-...>	Clear graph CLEAR GRAPH <http://example>
ClinVar - Count of Variants in genes f... PREFIX clinvar: <https://linkedlifedata.com/...>	Count of drugs according to the adve... PREFIX dco: <http://linkedlifedata.com/...>
Count the number of lipids per pathw...	Count the number of metabolites per...

Figure 9: BioGraphTalk KG

Figure 10: BioGraphTalk Class Relationship

The selected subgraph BioGraphTalk contains 141,317,128 total statement, from which 54,892,804 are explicit and 86,424,325 are inferred. The datasets included in BioGraphTalk are widely used in biomedical domain and are public or with license allowing usage for research purposes: Uniprot¹¹, WikiPathways¹², NCBI genes¹³, Drug Central¹⁴, ChEMBL¹⁵, Gene Ontology¹⁶, Clinvar¹⁷. BioGraphTalk is well aligned with Hereditary use cases. In Figure 10 and in Figure 11, some main class relationships and class hierarchy respectively are presented.

4.4 Methodology

4.4.1 Natural Language Querying

Natural language querying (NLQ) enables users to ask questions of a database using everyday, conversational language, rather than complex, formal query languages. In the context of GraphDB, a leading RDF graph database, this means you can interact with your data by simply typing or speaking questions in plain English.

Instead of writing intricate SPARQL queries (the standard query language for RDF databases), the user can ask something like, "Which are the genes associated with ALS? Please, provide a gene symbol, description and a stable identifier." GraphDB¹⁸, through its natural language querying capabilities, translates this question into a formal SPARQL query, executes it against the database, and returns the answer in a user-friendly format.

¹¹<https://www.uniprot.org/>

¹²<https://www.wikipathways.org/>

¹³<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/gene/>

¹⁴<https://drugcentral.org/>

¹⁵<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/chembl/>

¹⁶<https://geneontology.org/>

¹⁷<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/clinvar/>

¹⁸<https://www.ontotext.com/products/graphdb/>

Figure 11: BioGraphTalk Class Hierarchy

4.4.2 Implementation

GraphDB's Talk to Your Graph features provide an easy and customizable way to implement an NLQ application. The High-Level Architecture is shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12: The High-Level Architecture of how GraphDBs NLQ works.

The underlying flow shown in Figure 12 is as follows: first the user asks a natural language question to the LLM, and after receiving the question uses a set of tools provided to it to answer the question. The tools provided to LLM allow it to get certain information, such as the current time and date, or potentially even

search the web if needed. The most important tools are the ones that provide functionality to the LLM to interact with GraphDB and the data inside it. The tool allows the LLM to interact with the data using SPARQL queries, similarity indexes, and other sophisticated methods that allow the LLM to easily find and aggregate the needed information to answer the user's question and even provide its methodology if the user wishes to replicate or validate it.

Figure 13: GraphDB Talk To Your Graph setup

Zero-shot implementation we set up a Talk To Your Graph agent in GraphDB with ChatGPT 4.1 with temperature of 0 (Figure 13), in order to make the solution as deterministic as possible and always to return the most probable response, i.e. the one that is presented in the KG. The base instructions are:

```

1  "You are Quadro, an assistant developed by Ontotext and you can
2  answer questions about data stored in GraphDB. When answering a
3  question, you generally take a few steps.
4  First, you determine whether the question is relevant to the
5  ontology and let the user know if it seems to be out of scope of
6  the dataset you are working with.
7  Second, you identify the relevant entities in the question and
8  which would be objects in the \gls{kg}.
9  Third, you try to map each object to a URI in the database using an
10 appropriate tool such as autocomplete.
11 Fourth, you decide whether you need to get more results out of the
12 database using a SPARQL query or search method.
13 Finally, you use the collected information to answer the question."

```

The Additional instructions are:

```
1 "Your job is to help the user understand the molecular mechanisms
  of certain diseases and to identify explicit and hidden
  relationships between key research topics (like identifying
  which are the susceptibility genes for a particular disease/
  phenotype) and to provide provenance source for the extracted
  information based on the ontology provided. The NCBI gene
  ontology uses geneSymbol property for labels.
2
3 Always add the @en language tag at the end string literals for
  example VALUES ?diseaseLabel \{"Multiple Sclerosis"@en\}.
4 Always first use the full text search tool to find the IRIs.
5 The data is very large, so use VALUES instead of FILTER."
```

Multi-shot implementation For the Multi-shot implementation, we used the same base instructions. The prompt used for the additional instruction is:

```
1 Your job is to help the user understand the molecular mechanisms of
  certain diseases and to identify explicit and hidden relationships
  between key research topics (like identify which are the
  susceptibility genes for a particular disease/phenotype) and to
  provide provenance source for the extracted information based on the
  ontology provided. NCBI genes ontology uses geneSymbol property for
  labels.
2
3 Always add the @en language tag at the end string literals for example
  VALUES ?diseaseLabel {"Multiple Sclerosis"@en}.
4 Always first use the full text search tool to find the IRIs.
5 The data is very large, so use VALUES instead of FILTER.
6
7
8 Here are a few examples:
9
10 Which are the genes associated with Multiple Sclerosis?
11
12 The query to find the answer is:
13
14 PREFIX ncbigenes: <https://linkedlifedata.com/resource/ncbigenes/>
15 PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
16 PREFIX skos: <http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#>
17 select distinct ?gene ?geneSymbol where {
18     VALUES ?diseaseLabel {"Multiple Sclerosis"@en}
19     ?gene rdf:type ncbigenes:Gene;
20     ncbigenes:geneSymbol ?geneSymbol;
21     ?associatedWith ?disease.
22     ?disease ?label ?diseaseLabel .
23 }
24
```

```
25 Are there any associated pathways to these disorders , in which the
    identified genes participate?
26
27 query:
28
29 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
30 PREFIX td: <https://linkedlifedata.com/resource/targetdiscovery/ontology
    #>
31 PREFIX ncbigenes: <https://linkedlifedata.com/resource/ncbigenes/>
32 PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
33 PREFIX skos: <http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#>
34 #select distinct ?gene ?geneSymbol
35 select ?gene ?geneSymbol ?pathway ?descriptions ?labels
36 where {
37     VALUES ?diseaseLabel {"Multiple Sclerosis"@en}
38     ?gene rdf:type ncbigenes:Gene;
39         ncbigenes:geneSymbol ?geneSymbol;
40         td:encodes ?protein;
41         ?associatedWith ?disease.
42     ?disease ?label ?diseaseLabel .
43     ?protein td:isPartOf ?pathway;
44     skos:prefLabel ?prefLabel
45     OPTIONAL {?pathway skos:definition ?descriptions}
46     OPTIONAL {?pathway skos:prefLabel ?labels}
47 }
48
49 Find the hierarchy of Alzheimer?
50
51 query:
52
53 PREFIX skos: <http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#>
54 select * where {
55     <https://linkedlifedata.com/resource/umls/id/C0002395> skos:broader+
56     ?o .
57     ?o skos:prefLabel ?label
58 }
59
60 Which proteins are encoded by APP gene?
61
62 query:
63
64 PREFIX ncbigenes: <https://linkedlifedata.com/resource/ncbigenes/>
65 PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
66 select * where {
67     ?s ?p "APP" ;
68     rdf:type ncbigenes:Gene
69 }
```

4.5 Experiments and Results

For experiments we define competency questions that are either specific for some disease, gene etc., or explore more complex interrelations between multiple relations.

Here are sample questions for both types:

- (simple) Look for genes or proteins annotated with both gut and brain-related processes
- (simple) Which are the genes associated with Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis?
- (simple) Which proteins are encoded by APP gene?
- (complex) What are protein protein interactions between ALS and Parkinson disease?
- (complex) Which are genes related to ALS and MS?
- (complex) How does intestinal permeability (leaky gut) contribute to neuroinflammation?
- (complex) Can changes in diet or probiotics modulate the gut-brain axis and improve mental health outcomes?
- (complex) What molecular pathways are involved in gut-brain communication?

For these competence questions were done experiments both with zero-shot and multi-shot agents. For all simple questions, both agents successfully generated correct answers. However, the multi-shot agent was generally able to answer with fewer queries to GraphDB and also managed to answer more complex questions.

Multi-Shot experiment

For the question "What are protein protein interactions between ALS and Parkinson disease?" with the multi-shot agent we receive a result that contains the very comprehensive summary of the answer in natural language (Figure 14) as well as generated SPARQL query (Figure 15).

We can further copy the generated SPARQL query and run it directly in GraphDB over the BioGraphTalk to explore further and deep dive into specific complex relations between entities in the result to investigate the actual relations between them (Figure 16 and 17).

The manual validation by domain expert on the answer presents that the achieved results are sound and correct. The human validation of the result of SPARQL query presents that the extract.

4.6 Further work

The next steps include design of multiple agents related to different HEREDITARY use cases. Another direction in further work is related to implementation of demonstrator with user interface that will provide end-to-end functionalities of the TTYG without exposing to the end user the GraphDB triple store and will fully automate the process from natural language question to visual exploration of the KG relations. In addition, further work includes experiments with complex questions that can bring new insights in the gut-brain interplay. To ensure compliance with data protection - the current version of LLM - GPT will be also possible to be substitute with open LLMs using local model storage.

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL `https://ld-inventory.ontotext.com/demo/graphdb/ttyg`. The page title is "Talk to Your Graph". On the left is a navigation menu with options: Import, Explore, SPARQL, GraphQL, Monitor, Setup, Lab, **Talk to Your Graph**, and Help. The main content area shows a search bar with the query "HEREDITARY TTYG ... BioGraph...". Below the search bar, a text box contains the question: "What are protein protein interactions between ALS and Parkinson disease".

The system response is as follows:

To answer your question, I will:

1. Identify the relevant entities: "ALS" (Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis) and "Parkinson disease".
2. Find the genes/proteins associated with each disease.
3. Identify protein-protein interactions between the proteins associated with ALS and those associated with Parkinson disease.

Let me start by discovering the IRIs for 'ALS' and 'Parkinson disease' using full-text search.

Here are the protein-protein interactions between genes associated with ALS (Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis) and Parkinson disease, based on the knowledge graph:

Key interacting gene/protein pairs:

- Many ALS-associated proteins interact with PRKN (Parkin), a key Parkinson disease gene/protein.
- Some ALS proteins also interact with other Parkinson disease proteins such as DNAJC13, TMEM230, and TNK2.

Examples of protein-protein interactions:

ALS Gene (Protein)	Parkinson Gene (Protein)	Direction of Interaction
ANXA11 (P50995)	PRKN (X5DR79, O60260)	ALS→PD
ATXN2 (Q99700)	PRKN (X5DR79, O60260)	PD→ALS
C9orf72 (Q96LT7)	PRKN (X5DR79, O60260)	PD→ALS
CHRNA4 (P43681)	PRKN (X5DR79, O60260)	ALS→PD
DCTN1 (Q14203)	PRKN (X5DR79, O60260)	ALS→PD
DDX20 (Q9UHI6)	PRKN (X5DR79, O60260)	PD→ALS
DNAJC7 (Q99615)	PRKN (X5DR79, O60260)	PD→ALS
DYNC1H1 (Q14204)	PRKN (X5DR79, O60260)	ALS→PD
ELP3 (Q9H9T3)	PRKN (X5DR79, O60260)	PD→ALS
ERBB4 (Q15303)	TMEM230 (Q96A57)	ALS→PD
FRS3 (Q11944)	PRKN (X5DR79, O60260)	ALS→PD

At the bottom of the interface is an "Ask" button.

GraphDB 11.0.1 • RDF4J 5.1.2-jakarta • Connectors 16.3.2 • Workbench 3.0.1 • © 2002–2025 Ontotext AD. All rights reserved.

Figure 14: TTYG Experiment 1 - What are protein protein interactions between ALS and Parkinson disease? - the answer summary in natural language

The screenshot shows the GraphDB web interface. The browser address bar is `https://lld-inventory.ontotext.com/demo/graphdb/ttyg`. The page title is "Talk to Your Graph". On the left is a navigation menu with options: Import, Explore, SPARQL, GraphQL, Monitor, Setup, Lab, Talk to Your Graph (selected), and Help. The main content area shows a "Raw query" input field containing "HEREDITARY TTYG ..." and "BioGraph...". Below it, a "Called SPARQL: Direct query" window displays the following SPARQL query:

```

PREFIX ncbigenes:
<https://linkedlifedata.com/resource/ncbigenes/>
PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
PREFIX td:
<https://linkedlifedata.com/resource/targetdiscovery/ontology#>
PREFIX up: <http://purl.uniprot.org/core/>
PREFIX skos: <http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#>

SELECT DISTINCT ?alsGene ?alsGeneSymbol ?alsProtein ?pdGene ?
pdGeneSymbol ?pdProtein ?interaction
WHERE {
  VALUES ?alsDisease
  {<https://linkedlifedata.com/resource/umls/id/C0002736>} # ALS
  VALUES ?pdDisease
  {<https://linkedlifedata.com/resource/umls/id/C0038567>} #
  Parkinson Disease

  ?alsGene rdf:type ncbigenes:Gene ;
    ncbigenes:geneSymbol ?alsGeneSymbol ;
    td:associatedWith ?alsDisease ;
    td:encodes ?alsProtein .
  ?pdGene rdf:type ncbigenes:Gene ;
    ncbigenes:geneSymbol ?pdGeneSymbol ;
    td:associatedWith ?pdDisease ;
    td:encodes ?pdProtein .

  # Protein-protein interaction
  { ?alsProtein td:interactsWith ?pdProtein . BIND("ALS->PD" AS
?interaction) }
  UNION
  { ?pdProtein td:interactsWith ?alsProtein . BIND("PD->ALS" AS
?interaction) }

  # Optionally get protein labels
  OPTIONAL { ?alsProtein skos:prefLabel ?alsProteinLabel }
  OPTIONAL { ?pdProtein skos:prefLabel ?pdProteinLabel }
}
ORDER BY ?alsGeneSymbol ?pdGeneSymbol
  
```

At the bottom of the interface, there is an "Ask" button and a footer with the text: "GraphDB 11.0.1 • RDF4J 5.1.2-jakarta • Connectors 16.3.2 • Workbench 3.0.1 • © 2002–2025 Ontotext AD. All rights reserved."

Figure 15: TTYG Experiment 1 - What are protein protein interactions between ALS and Parkinson disease? - the generated SPARQL query

Figure 16: TTYG Experiment 1 - What are protein protein interactions between ALS and Parkinson disease? - the generated SPARQL query run in GraphDB over BioGraphTalk

Figure 17: TTYG Experiment 1 - What are protein protein interactions between ALS and Parkinson disease? - visual exploration of the result in GraphDB over BioGraphTalk

5 Neurodegen-Vis: LLM-based, Privacy-Preserving Visual Exploration of High-Dimensional ALS, PD, MS Patient Data

5.1 Introduction

Medical datasets can be highly complex, ranging from measurements to social demographics. Visual Analytics (VA) approaches help users to get an understanding of the data, clusters, and relationships among variables.

Figure 18: The Dashboard, Correlation Heatmap on the left, Scatterplot and biplot on the right. In the biplot a Principal Component Analysis (PCA) can be started, and the number of clusters can be selected dynamically. In the biplot and the scatterplot the PCA clusters are colored. On the very left is the chatbot. The *suggest feature* function was used for exploration. They are highlighted in the correlation heatmap (sixth row on the very left) and additionally shown in the Scatterplot. In the chatbot window, it is explained why the features are interesting to analyze.

However, users face various challenges when interaction with a dashboard about complex data. Firstly, the user may have questions about the dataset itself, because of different conventions about feature names, or because they are not a domain expert. Secondly, the user may have problems understanding the dashboard itself. Perhaps they do not understand the individual visualisations, how to select the views of interest, and how the different parts of the dashboard interact with each other. Thirdly, during data exploration, it can be hard to identify interesting aspects, or where to start with data exploration.

Motivated by these challenges, we designed and implemented an interactive dashboard to identify correlations, dependencies, and groups within a dataset about Parkinson's disease patients via VA, cf. Figure 18 for a screenshot of the primary view after data anonymisation and configuration. As a key functionality, we

equip the tool with a seamless LM integration, aiming to assist the user. The LM is provided information about the dashboard and the dataset. Combined with the general world-knowledge of LM's it can help the user with exploration and explanation (see Example 1). The user has a classic, familiar chatbot interface to interact with. Additionally, the LM is used to highlight and explain different views of the dashboard (cf. Examples 2 and 3).

Especially for critical data domains such as healthcare, the interpretation and conclusions should still be made by the user dependent on the data, not the LM. Therefore, our focus is on explaining and exploring the dashboard and the data, rather than giving interpretations, and results only if the user can verify them on the dashboard. For these applications VA and LM's very much suit each other, as the user can always verify everything the LM's says, and the LM can enhance the dashboard by helping the user in understanding and exploration.

What is the correlation between age and language z test and what does this suggest?

The correlation between age (insnpsi_age) and the language z test (language_z_comp) is -0.413. This negative correlation suggests that as age increases, scores on the language z test tend to decrease. In other words, older patients may generally perform worse on language-related cognitive tasks compared to younger patients.

Example 1: Chatbot integration: the user can ask questions to interpret correlations in the real data, without the LM ever seeing any of the data per se, only differentially private analysis results from it.

In this chapter we analyze the LM implementation for a dashboard to analyze health care data of patients with Parkinson disease. In the dashboard, the focus lies on identifying correlations, dependencies, and groups within a dataset.

5.1.1 Dataset

The dataset contains information on patients with PD. It comprises approximately 100 features for 50 patients. It includes demographic data such as patient age and duration of PD diagnosis, alongside results from various cognitive tests and treatment details. Several columns contain redundant information, with some measurements represented both numerically and categorically. Additionally, cognitive tests were conducted using multiple methodologies, leading to potential domain shifts. Binary indicators in the dataset denote the use of specific test methods.

After accounting for duplicate information and test method markers, the dataset includes approximately 15 unique measurements.

5.1.2 Anonymisation using Differential Privacy

In order to protect patients' private data, our tool anonymises the incoming dataset before displaying it to a (potentially unauthorised) user. In a first step, names and directly personally identifiable information is stripped away, which only requires users to specify which columns are affected. But of course, this still leaves highly personal direct measurements of the patients' health characteristic, as deemed necessary in conducting the recording of the dataset.

Specifically, we generate (an arbitrary amount of) synthetic tabular data based on the distribution of features across the input dataset. As such tabular data is often a mix of ordinal, categorical and continuous

features, we have to treat them separately in the anonymisation phase. The categorical data is synthetically generated based on the Multiplicative Weights Exponential Mechanism (MWEM) (Hardt et al., 2012), with an implementation in the third-party package `smartnoise-sdk`, developed by OpenDP¹⁹ (and based on their formally verified `opendp` library). Next up, the continuous columns are then only sampled from their respective input distributions. For simplicity of this demonstrator, we assume a normal distribution in all numerical columns (also taking bounds and, for example, integer constraints into account). This still faces our generation procedure with the challenge of preserving correlations. Correlation can be preserved using randomized order, correlation-integrated sampling from the respective feature distributions. One starts by obtaining a (Pearson-) correlation matrix $C \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ of the respective input features (in our case, a roughly 60x60 matrix) and passing it through the MWEM implementation to skew it with noise and making it differentially private with respect to the input data. During the sampling procedure, in random order, the columns are sampled from their respective (normal) distributions parametrised earlier. Each sample value is then skewed according to the correlation between all previously sampled values and the feature correlation contained in C . The output dataset then approximately follows the input distribution and keeps correlations consistent. The dashboard and corresponding LM interaction (and, of course, the figures included in this work) now only rely on the synthetically generated data.

5.2 Related Work

Visualization and analysis of high-dimensional data is a long-standing challenge in data science, and to date many approaches for interactive exploration of this data have been proposed. The Rank by Feature framework (Seo & Shneiderman, 2006) was among the first approaches to identify and rank data features by their correlation, hence supporting the user in selecting interesting and relevant data. It used a heatmap to show the feature importance. In general, tabular data can be interactively visualized by general tools like spreadsheet software, and specialized development suites like Tableau or Microsoft PowerBI. Lineup (Gratzl et al., 2013) is a tabular data visualization specifically for comparing and ranking the rows of a multivariate table, having the user interactively find appropriate weights for the different features. Scatter Plot matrices and scatter plots are widely-used tools to show an overview of pairwise correlations, amenable for overviewing and searching (Chegini et al., 2018). Recently, Language Model technology has drastically advanced the capability of Natural Language Processing, and existing implementations like Llama or ChatGPT allow to integrate LM-based Natural Language Interfaces (NLIs) into interactive visualization applications. There are many roles where LMs can help users to navigate and understand visualizations and data, as presented in the framework in (Zhao et al., 2025).

In our work, we design a dashboard for exploring tabular data of numeric and categorical values. We make use of existing visualizations like correlation heatmaps, scatter plots, and principal components plots. While these techniques are not novel, in many case studies they have shown to be very understandable and an expert tool for data exploration. Our main contribution is the intergration of an LLM interface to assist the user, and to apply it to a anonymized real-world health data set. Our use case shows the dashboard design and LLM intergration are helpful and hence can allow for explaining and guiding users.

¹⁹<https://opendp.org/>

Figure 19: The feature *language z-component* in the histogram view. Colour coded is the categorical feature *z-diagnosis*.

5.3 Visualisation Approach & Methods

Currently, there is a high amount of interest in the interaction of LM and VA interfaces in the Visual Analytics community. The framework to describe our dashboard to the Generative Pre-trained Transformer (GPT) was inspired by (Zhao et al., 2025). Hutchinson shortly describes what challenges and opportunities LMs provide for Visual Analytics (Hutchinson et al., 2024).

In Neurodegen-Vis, a correlation heatmap (cf. Figure 18), scatterplots (cf. Figures 20a and 20b), and histograms (cf. Figure 19) are used to provide an overview of the data and enable the exploration of variable dependencies. For cognitive z-scores, which were obtained using different test methods, the visualization colour-codes these methods and shows average values, to identify potential shifts due to methodological changes. Furthermore, a PCA analysis, can be applied to detect underlying group structures. The results are presented as biplots for interpretability. The different clusters are colour coded in the biplot, and can also be selected to be colour coded in the scatterplot, to further analyse the influence of the original features and how they could be clustered.

5.3.1 Natural Language Interface

The LM should enhance the understanding and exploration of the dashboard knowledge, including information about the datasets, feature descriptions, details about the dashboard itself, and general world knowledge. The user can interact with the LM within a classic chatbot interface, and additionally the LM implementation can highlight cells of the correlation heatmap and change the scatterplot view.

The chatbot can explain the different features (see Example 3). This is helpful for clarifying ambiguous terms to experts and can help non-domain experts to understand the data. It is not only convenient to have the feature descriptions within the dashboard itself (rather than in a separate document), but with the Chatbot's world knowledge, the chatbot is also capable of providing more complex answers to follow-up questions and dashboard-specific queries. Moreover, it ensures that everyone who has access to the dashboard also has access to this knowledge base, reducing the chance of misunderstandings or inconsistencies. It also enables interactive explanation and exploration of the dashboard (see Example 2). It can explain individual views in detail (e.g., what a biplot is) as well as their interactions and the deeper meanings behind the visualizations on the website.

Can you explain the components of the dashboard?

The Parkinson's Disease Visual Analytics Dashboard consists of three main components:

1. Pearson Correlation Heatmap:
 - Type: Heatmap
 - Function: Displays the Pearson correlation coefficients between different features related to patients with Parkinson's disease.
 - Interaction: Clicking on a cell will update the Feature Scatterplot based on the selected feature pair.
2. Feature Scatterplot:
 - Type: Scatterplot
 - Function: ...
3. PCA Biplot:

Example 2: Dashboard explanation using the LM integration.

As seen in Example 1, the chatbot also has access to results of the data correlations, enabling it to make more informed suggestions and assist in analyzing and understanding the dashboard. The "suggest features" function helps the user explore the dataset and discover interesting aspects in the data. It not only suggests notable features but also highlights them visually. As seen in Figure 18 the cell in the correlation heatmap is highlighted, and it changes the scatterplot to the suggested features.

This aspect is especially important to us, as the user should continue focusing on the numerical and graphical information to draw insights, rather than relying solely on ChatGPT's analysis or that of any other LLM, most notably locally hosted models. Replacing the default Language Model integration with a local alternative is effortless, only requiring the user to supply a different API endpoint configuration. Through this interaction, we allow the user to explore the dataset more intuitively, while still being able to draw their own conclusions and verify findings independently.

(a) Scatterplot of two features in the data, coloured according to the k-means cluster results.

(b) Principal Component Analysis view.

What is the feature `overall_domain_sum` and why could it be interesting to analyze?

The feature "overall_domain_sum" represents the total number of cognitive assessment tests in which a patient did not achieve adequate scores across various cognitive domains (such as attentional, executive, visuospatial, memory, and language). It is a cumulative measure reflecting the severity of cognitive impairment. Analyzing this feature can be interesting because it helps to quantify the extent of cognitive deficits in patients with Parkinson's disease. A higher overall domain sum indicates more significant cognitive impairment, which could impact the patient's daily functioning and quality of life. It can also help in understanding correlations with other clinical measures, treatment responses, and overall disease progression, aiding in personalised medical decision-making.

Example 3: Feature explanation using the LM.

5.4 Implementation

The dashboard was implemented as a *React*²⁰ application using *TypeScript*. Plots were created with the *observableHQ*²¹ and *D3*²² libraries to enhance interactivity. All calculations were performed in the TypeScript frontend. The dataset's small size (under 100 KB) made this feasible. For the heatmap the standard pearson correlation was used, and in the scatterplot the k-means++ algorithm was used. The OpenAI API was used to facilitate usage based on the model "gpt-4o-mini". The chatbot was given a system prompt that it is a helpful chatbot for a Visual Analytics dashboard and should give short and precise answers. Additionally, to gain domain knowledge, the chatbot was given the feature descriptions of all features and a jsx file which described the components and interaction between the different views. The framework was adopted from Zhao et al (Zhao et al., 2025). The "suggest features" function additionally changes the view of the highlights the features on the heatmap, and changes the view of the dashboard. Therefore, an output needed to be a list of two features. This works robustly with a standard prompt, which strictly defines the format and emphasises that no additional text should be used. Afterwards, the chatbot should explain its answer, which is shown to the user in the chatbot window.

5.5 Use Case

We demonstrate the applicability of our system on a use case involving the exploration of the relations between attributes of patient's information. This explorative approach is enabled through heatmaps and scatterplots, allowing the identification of linear dependencies. One such observation found through our system might be that cognitive performance declines with increasing age (*insnpsi_age*), while the duration of PD diagnosis has little effect on test scores. Figure 18 illustrates a scatterplot comparing the *visual z-score* with patient age. It reveals that patients who took the CDT test exhibit different average scores, which could potentially skew the data. This should be accounted for in subsequent analyses. In the PCA biplot, users can select features of interest to visualise their influence on the principal components. Scatterplots and histograms are dynamically generated by clicking on non-diagonal and diagonal cells of the heatmap, respectively, with test methods selectable via a dropdown menu.

²⁰<https://react.dev/>

²¹<https://observablehq.com/documentation/cells/observable-javascript>

²²<https://d3js.org/>

5.6 Conclusion & Future Work

We presented a comprehensive data exploration dashboard integrated with a Language Model to enable non-expert users to work with the data as well. As our use case focuses on patient data, we also explained how to anonymise it beforehand, resulting in a synthetically generated dataset of 100 entries, which we then visualise in the dashboard.

In the current state, the chatbot only interacts with the dashboard with the suggest features button. There could be more actions defined, where interactions with the dashboard could be useful. Furthermore, the chatbot answers questions when they are submitted and interacts with the dashboard with a different button. This could be done dynamically from the user's side, where with every prompt it is checked whether highlighting or interacting with the dashboard provides more insights, and the tool then does so if needed. For example, when a feature should be explained, it should also be highlighted in the correlation heatmap and shown in the histogram view. The dashboard could be generalised for different datasets, and in a perfectly integrated data environment, the most interesting dataset or data view could be loaded using the LM. Future work should also evaluate the effectiveness and precision provided by the various available LMs.

6 Summary and Further Development

This deliverable contains three novel querying approaches for natural language and visual retrieval. These tools combine both aspects to benefit from advantages and advances, especially in NLP, to deliver systems beneficial for both users that are non-experts in the use-case domains, and non-experts at formulating queries in specialized languages.

The integration of the complementary natural language and visual interfaces, however, requires careful integration of both fields to arrive at a well-integrated system. This interplay can be tested through further evaluation within our systems, especially within the scope of user studies and use-case evaluation by experts within the medical domains we support. This is the goal of the HEREDITARY task 5.5 (Requirements analysis, evaluation, and user studies). The introduced querying components will be further developed by requirement analysis and evaluation. As the preliminary evaluations in this deliverable have shown, LLM-based interfaces have great potential to inform users of different knowledge levels. They can even inspire and motivate new queries which users have not thought about before. In this regard, in task 5.4 (User guidance approaches) we will further develop workflows and approaches to support and guide the user towards insightful data exploration, and to obtain new insights in large multimodal, and heterogeneous data sets.

We intend to gather further feedback by scientific outreach. First, the OnSET toolkit will be presented on the SIGIR 2025 conference (Kantz et al., 2025). The Neurodegen-Vis tool will be presented at the ECAI-2025 Workshop on User-Centered Explanations in XAI (UCEX-XAI). Furthermore, we work on scientific publications of various further aspects of our work on querying components for KGs.

Additional effort will also be placed in integrating these distinct tools into one platform, enabling broader access to the public and improving consistency between tools. First steps could be the inclusion of the TTYG into OnSET as a chat interface to retrieve tabular data and interact with the prototype query graph consistently.

References

- Abu-Aisheh, Z., Raveaux, R., Ramel, J.-Y., & Martineau, P. (2015). An Exact Graph Edit Distance Algorithm for Solving Pattern Recognition Problems. *4th International Conference on Pattern Recognition Applications and Methods 2015*. <https://doi.org/10.5220/0005209202710278>
- Affolter, K., Stockinger, K., & Bernstein, A. (2019). A comparative survey of recent natural language interfaces for databases. *The VLDB Journal*, 28(5), 793–819. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00778-019-00567-8>
- Alper, B., Bach, B., Henry Riche, N., Isenberg, T., & Fekete, J.-D. (2013). Weighted graph comparison techniques for brain connectivity analysis. *Proceedings of the SIGCHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems - CHI '13*, 483. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2470654.2470724>
Comparison of weighted graphs.
- Andrews, K., Wohlfahrt, M., & Wurzinger, G. (2009). Visual graph comparison. *2009 13th International Conference Information Visualisation*, 62–67. <https://doi.org/10.1109/IV.2009.108>
- Arazzi, M., Ligari, D., Nicolazzo, S., & Nocera, A. (2025). Augmented knowledge graph querying leveraging llms. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2502.01298*.
- Avila, C. V. S., Casanova, M. A., & Vidal, V. M. (2024). A framework for question answering on knowledge graphs using large language models. *European Semantic Web Conference*, 168–172.
- Bast, H., & Buchhold, B. (2017). Qlever: A query engine for efficient sparql+text search. *Proceedings of the 2017 ACM on Conference on Information and Knowledge Management*, 647–656. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3132847.3132921>
- Beck, F., Burch, M., Diehl, S., & Weiskopf, D. (2017). A taxonomy and survey of dynamic graph visualization. *Comput. Graph. Forum*, 36(1), 133–159. <https://doi.org/10.1111/CGF.12791>
- Behrisch, M., Davey, J., Simon, S., Schreck, T., Keim, D., & Kohlhammer, J. (2013). Visual comparison of orderings and rankings. *EuroVis Workshop on Visual Analytics*.
- Bostock, M., Ogievetsky, V., & Heer, J. (2011). D3: Data-driven documents. *IEEE Trans. Visualization & Comp. Graphics (Proc. InfoVis)*. <http://vis.stanford.edu/papers/d3>
- Both, A., & Perevalov, A. (2024). Towards llm-driven natural language generation based on sparql queries and rdf knowledge graphs. In S. Tiwari, N. Mihindukulasooriya, F. Osborne, D. Kontokostas, J. D. 0001, M. Kejriwal, M. A. Pellegrino, A. Rula, J. E. L. Gayo, M. Cochez, & M. Alam (Eds.), *Joint proceedings of the 3rd International workshop on knowledge graph generation from text (TEXT2KG) and Data Quality meets Machine Learning and Knowledge Graphs (DQMLKG) co-located with the Extended Semantic Web Conference (ESWC 2024)* (p. 14, Vol. 3747). CEUR-WS.org. https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3747/text2kg_paper14.pdf
- Brandes, U., Dwyer, T., & Schreiber, F. (2004). Visual understanding of metabolic pathways across organisms using layout in two and a half dimensions. *Journal of Integrative Bioinformatics*, 1(1). <https://doi.org/10.1515/jib-2004-2>
Stacked 2.5-dimensional graphs for comparison.
- Chau, D. H., Faloutsos, C., Tong, H., Hong, J. I., Gallagher, B., & Eliassi-Rad, T. (2008). Graphite: A visual query system for large graphs. *2008 IEEE International Conference on Data Mining Workshops*, 963–966. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICDMW.2008.99>

- Chegini, M., Shao, L., Gregor, R., Lehmann, D. J., Andrews, K., & Schreck, T. (2018). Interactive visual exploration of local patterns in large scatterplot spaces. *Comput. Graph. Forum*, 37(3), 99–109. <https://doi.org/10.1111/CGF.13404>
- Clemmer, A., & Davies, S. (2011). Smeagol: A “specific-to-general” semantic web query interface paradigm for novices. In A. Hameurlain, S. W. Liddle, K.-D. Schewe, & X. Zhou (Eds.), *Database and expert systems applications* (pp. 288–302). Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
- Diehl, S., Carsten, G., & Kerren, A. (2001). Preserving the mental map using foresighted layout. *Data Visualization 2001: Proceedings of the Joint Eurographics—IEEE TCVG Symposium on Visualization*, 175–184. Retrieved December 12, 2019, from <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/4203/2fb4313b6e419ff74a1ee2a2047ceb9970e3.pdf>
- Emonet, V., Bolleman, J. T., Duvaud, S., de Farias, T. M., & Sima, A. C. (2024). Llm-based SPARQL query generation from natural language over federated knowledge graphs. In R. Alharbi, J. de Berardinis, P. Groth, A. Meroño-Peñuela, E. Simperl, & V. Tamma (Eds.), *Proceedings of the special session on harmonising generative AI and semantic web technologies (HGALS 2024) co-located with the 23rd international semantic web conference (ISWC 2024), baltimore, maryland, november 13, 2024* (Vol. 3953). CEUR-WS.org. <https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3953/355.pdf>
- Faggioli, G., Marchesin, S., Menotti, L., Nunzio, G. M. D., Silvello, G., & Ferro, N. (2024). The brain-teaser ontology for als and ms clinical data. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.12789731>
- Faggioli, G., Menotti, L., Marchesin, S., Chió, A., Dagliati, A., de Carvalho, M., Gromicho, M., Manera, U., Tavazzi, E., Di Nunzio, G. M., Silvello, G., & Ferro, N. (2024). An extensible and unifying approach to retrospective clinical data modeling: The brainteaser ontology. *Journal of Biomedical Semantics*, 15(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13326-024-00317-y>
- Ferré, S. (2016). Sparklis: An expressive query builder for sparql endpoints with guidance in natural language. *Semantic Web*, 8(3), 405–418. <https://doi.org/10.3233/SW-150208>
- Francart, T. (2023). Sparnatural: A visual knowledge graph exploration tool. *European Semantic Web Conference*, 11–15.
- García, R., López-Gil, J.-M., & Gil, R. (2022). Rhizomer: Interactive semantic knowledge graphs exploration. *SoftwareX*, 20, 101235. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.softx.2022.101235>
- Gladisch, S., Schumann, H., Ernst, M., Füllen, G., & Tominski, C. (2014). Semi-automatic editing of graphs with customized layouts. *Computer Graphics Forum*, 33(3), 381–390. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1111/cgf.12394>
- Gratzl, S., Lex, A., Gehlenborg, N., Pfister, H., & Streit, M. (2013). Lineup: Visual analysis of multi-attribute rankings. *IEEE Trans. Vis. Comput. Graph.*, 19(12), 2277–2286. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TVCG.2013.173>
- Grootendorst, M. (2022). Bertopic: Neural topic modeling with a class-based tf-idf procedure. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2203.05794*.
- Gruber, T. R. (1995). Toward principles for the design of ontologies used for knowledge sharing? *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies*, 43(5), 907–928. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1006/ijhc.1995.1081>

- Hardt, M., Ligett, K., & McSherry, F. (2012, December). A simple and practical algorithm for differentially private data release. In *Guide Proceedings* (pp. 2339–2347, Vol. 2). Curran Associates Inc. <https://doi.org/10.5555/2999325.2999396>
- Hogan, A., Blomqvist, E., Cochez, M., D'amato, C., Melo, G. D., Gutierrez, C., Kirrane, S., Gayo, J. E. L., Navigli, R., Neumaier, S., Ngomo, A.-C. N., Polleres, A., Rashid, S. M., Rula, A., Schmelzeisen, L., Sequeda, J., Staab, S., & Zimmermann, A. (2021). Knowledge graphs. *ACM Comput. Surv.*, 54(4). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3447772>
- Hutchinson, M., Jianu, R., Slingsby, A., & Madhyastha, P. (2024). Llm-assisted visual analytics: Opportunities and challenges. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2409.02691*.
- Jadhav, S., Perumal, S., Tadavi, Y., Dash, B., & Parthiban, S. (2025). Leveraging large language models for biomedical knowledge graph construction and querying: An advanced nlp approach. *Companion Proceedings of the ACM on Web Conference 2025*, 2560–2566.
- Ji, Z., Lee, N., Frieske, R., Yu, T., Su, D., Xu, Y., Ishii, E., Bang, Y. J., Madotto, A., & Fung, P. (2023). Survey of hallucination in natural language generation. *ACM Comput. Surv.*, 55(12). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3571730>
- Jia, R., Zhang, B., Méndez, S. J. R., & Omran, P. G. (2024). Leveraging large language models for semantic query processing in a scholarly knowledge graph. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2405.15374*.
- Kantz, B., Innerebner, K., Waldert, P., Lengauer, S., Lex, E., & Schreck, T. (2025). Onset: Ontology and semantic exploration toolkit. *Proceedings of the 48th International ACM SIGIR Conference on Research and Development in Information Retrieval*, 3980–3984. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3726302.3730148>
- Krause, J., Perer, A., & Stavropoulos, H. (2016). Supporting iterative cohort construction with visual temporal queries. *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics*, 22(1), 91–100. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TVCG.2015.2467622>
- Kusupati, A., Bhatt, G., Rege, A., Wallingford, M., Sinha, A., Ramanujan, V., Howard-Snyder, W., Chen, K., Kakade, S. M., Jain, P., & Farhadi, A. (2022). Matryoshka representation learning. In A. H. Oh, A. Agarwal, D. Belgrave, & K. Cho (Eds.), *Advances in neural information processing systems*. <https://openreview.net/forum?id=9njZa1fm35>
- Lehmann, J., Gattogi, P., Bhandiwad, D., Ferré, S., & Vahdati, S. (2023). Language models as controlled natural language semantic parsers for knowledge graph question answering. In *Ecai 2023* (pp. 1348–1356). IOS Press.
- Lehmann, J., Isele, R., Jakob, M., Jentzsch, A., Kontokostas, D., Mendes, P. N., Hellmann, S., Morsey, M., van Kleef, P., Auer, S., & Bizer, C. (2015). Dbpedia - a large-scale, multilingual knowledge base extracted from wikipedia. *Semantic Web*, 6, 167–195. <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:1181640>
- Lei, C., Özcan, F., Quamar, A., Mittal, A. R., Sen, J., Saha, D., & Sankaranarayanan, K. (2018). Ontology-based natural language query interfaces for data exploration. *IEEE Data Eng. Bull.*, 41(3), 52–63.
- Lissandrini, M., Mottin, D., Palpanas, T., & Velegarakis, Y. (2020). Graph-query suggestions for knowledge graph exploration. *Proceedings of The Web Conference 2020*, 2549–2555. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3366423.3380005>

- Liu, M. X., Liu, F., Fiannaca, A. J., Koo, T., Dixon, L., Terry, M., & Cai, C. J. (2024). “we need structured output”: Towards user-centered constraints on large language model output. *Extended Abstracts of the CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3613905.3650756>
- Liu, P., Wang, X., Fu, Q., Yang, Y., Li, Y.-F., & Zhang, Q. (2022). Kgvql: A knowledge graph visual query language with bidirectional transformations. *Knowledge-Based Systems*, 250, 108870. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.knosys.2022.108870>
- Liu, S., Semnani, S. J., Triedman, H., Xu, J., Zhao, I. D., & Lam, M. S. (2024). SPINACH: sparql-based information navigation for challenging real-world questions. In Y. Al-Onaizan, M. Bansal, & Y. Chen (Eds.), *Findings of the association for computational linguistics: EMNLP 2024, miami, florida, usa, november 12-16, 2024* (pp. 15977–16001). Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://aclanthology.org/2024.findings-emnlp.938>
- llama.cpp authors. (2025, February). Gbnf guide [[Online; accessed 2025-02-11]]. <https://github.com/ggerganov/llama.cpp/blob/b9ab0a4d0b2ed19effec130921d05fb5c30b68c5/grammars/README.md>
- Menotti, L., & Silvello, G. (2024). The hereditary ontology for genomics data [Accessed: 2024-10-01]. <https://hereditary.dei.unipd.it/ontology/genomics/>
- Meyer, L.-P., Frey, J., Brei, F., & Arndt, N. (2024). Assessing sparql capabilities of large language models. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2409.05925>
- Muennighoff, N., Tazi, N., Magne, L., & Reimers, N. (2022). Mteb: Massive text embedding benchmark. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2210.07316*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2210.07316>
- Ongri, J. G., Tijtrahardja, E., Darari, F., & Ekaputra, F. J. (2024). Towards an open nli llm-based system for kgs: A case study of wikidata. *2024 7th International Seminar on Research of Information Technology and Intelligent Systems (ISRITI)*, 44–49.
- Peng, C., Xia, F., Naseriparsa, M., & Osborne, F. (2023). Knowledge graphs: Opportunities and challenges. *Artificial Intelligence Review*, 56(11), 13071–13102. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10462-023-10465-9>
- Pérez-Messina, I., Ceneda, D., & Miksch, S. (2023). A Methodology for Task-Driven Guidance Design. In M. Angelini & M. El-Assady (Eds.), *Eurovis workshop on visual analytics (eurova)*. The Eurographics Association. <https://doi.org/10.2312/eurova.20231094>
- Pienta, R., Tamersoy, A., Endert, A., Navathe, S., Tong, H., & Chau, D. H. (2016). Visage: Interactive visual graph querying. *Proceedings of the International Working Conference on Advanced Visual Interfaces*, 272–279. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2909132.2909246>
- Qwen, : Yang, A., Yang, B., Zhang, B., Hui, B., Zheng, B., Yu, B., Li, C., Liu, D., Huang, F., Wei, H., Lin, H., Yang, J., Tu, J., Zhang, J., Yang, J., Yang, J., Zhou, J., . . . Qiu, Z. (2025). Qwen2.5 technical report. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2412.15115>
- Reimers, N., & Gurevych, I. (2019). Sentence-bert: Sentence embeddings using siamese bert-networks. *Proceedings of the 2019 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing*. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1908.10084>
- Sannigrahi, S., Fraga-Silva, T., Oualil, Y., & Van Gysel, C. (2024). Synthetic query generation using large language models for virtual assistants. *Proceedings of the 47th International ACM SI-*

- GIR Conference on Research and Development in Information Retrieval*, 2837–2841. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3626772.3661355>
- Seaborne, A., Taelman, R., Williams, G., Hartig, O., & Tanon, T. P. (2024, December). *SPARQL 1.2 query language* (W3C Working Draft) (<https://www.w3.org/TR/2024/WD-sparql12-query-20241227/>). W3C.
- Seo, J., & Shneiderman, B. (2006). Knowledge discovery in high-dimensional data: Case studies and a user survey for the rank-by-feature framework. *IEEE Trans. Vis. Comput. Graph.*, 12(3), 311–322. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TVCG.2006.50>
- Teknium, R., Quesnelle, J., & Guang, C. (2024). Hermes 3 technical report. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2408.11857>
- Urchade, Z., Tomeh, N., Holat, P., & Charnois, T. (2024). An autoregressive text-to-graph framework for joint entity and relation extraction.
- Vargas, H., Buil-Aranda, C., Hogan, A., & López, C. (2019). Rdf explorer: A visual sparql query builder. In C. Ghidini, O. Hartig, M. Maleshkova, V. Svátek, I. Cruz, A. Hogan, J. Song, M. Lefrançois, & F. Gandon (Eds.), *The semantic web – iswc 2019* (pp. 647–663). Springer International Publishing.
- White, R. W., & Roth, R. A. (2009). *Exploratory search: Beyond the query—response paradigm*. Springer International Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-02260-9>
- Zhang, D., Li, J., Zeng, Z., & Wang, F. (2025). Jasper and stella: Distillation of sota embedding models. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2412.19048>
- Zhao, Y., Zhang, Y., Zhang, Y., Zhao, X., Wang, J., Shao, Z., Turkay, C., & Chen, S. (2025). Leva: Using large language models to enhance visual analytics. *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics*, 31(3), 1830–1847. <https://doi.org/10.1109/tvcg.2024.3368060>